

CAMPUS JOURNALISM PARTICIPATION AND LANGUAGE PROFICIENCY AMONG ELEMENTARY SCHOOL LEARNERS IN STA. CRUZ NORTH DISTRICT

SANIE G. MONCHING

Abstract. The study unfolded the extent of campus journalism participation and its association with language proficiency among Elementary School learners in Sta Cruz North District, Davao del Sur Schools Division. The study used non-experimental descriptive-correlational research design, where it utilized adapted survey instrument to gather responses from the randomly selected teacher-respondents. Data gathered were treated using Mean scores with descriptive interpretation, Pearson r and Simple Linear Regression Analysis. Findings revealed that the extent of campus journalism participation in terms of regularity of publication, community engagement, quality of content, awards and recognition and student leadership denotes moderately extensive, and likewise with learners' language proficiency in terms of speaking and listening skills, writing skills, vocabulary knowledge, language awareness and reading comprehension. There is a significant relationship between campus journalism participation and language proficiency among elementary school learners. Domains of campus journalism participation in terms of regularity of publication, quality of content, student leadership and awards and recognition significantly influenced language proficiency. Promoting community engagement, schools can create a supportive and stimulating environment for language learning and development.

KEY WORDS

1. campus journalism 2. language proficiency 3. journalism participation

1. Introduction

Language proficiency is a critical skill for learners of all ages and is linked to academic success and future opportunities. Campus journalism participation is one extracurricular activity that may offer opportunities for learners to develop language skills, including reading, writing, speaking, listening, and vocabulary. However, despite the potential benefits of campus journalism participation for language proficiency, there is a gap in research that specifically examines the relationship between these two factors. The participation of elementary learners in campus journalism has been seen as a way to enhance their language proficiency skills (Delos Reyes Pineda, 2021; Pineda, 2018). However, there are still gaps in research on this topic that need to be addressed. This essay will discuss the research gaps on learners' language proficiency given campus journalism participation from 2018 to 2022. One of the research gaps is the lack of studies that specifically measure the impact of campus journalism participation on

the language proficiency of elementary learners. While there have been studies that show a correlation between participation in campus journalism and language proficiency (Delos Reyes Pineda, 2021; Pineda, 2018), there is still a need for research that focuses on the extent of this impact. This will help provide a clearer understanding of how much participation in campus journalism contributes to language proficiency improvement. Another research gap is the limited studies that focus on the role of campus journalism in enhancing the different aspects of language proficiency, such as reading, writing, listening, and speaking. Most studies tend to focus on the impact of campus journalism on general language proficiency, without specifying which aspect of language proficiency was improved (Delos Reyes Pineda, 2021; Pineda, 2018). Future studies should aim to identify which aspect of language proficiency is most affected by campus journalism participation. Another research gap is the need for studies that compare the impact of campus journalism participation on language proficiency with other language learning interventions, such as storytelling or drama. This would help identify the unique contribution of campus journalism to language proficiency improvement and its potential advantages over other language learning interventions. The Philippine education system puts a premium on language proficiency, recognizing its importance in communication and understanding. Elementary campus journalism, as part of the curriculum, plays a significant role in enhancing students' language proficiency. Despite the emphasis on campus journalism as a tool for enhancing language proficiency, there is a dearth of comprehensive studies that explore its impact on students' language skills. Most studies on campus journalism only focus on its impact on students' socio-emotional development and writing skills, leaving language proficiency out of the equation (Gonzales et al., 2020). Without a comprehensive understanding of the impact of campus journalism on language proficiency, educators cannot design effective programs and strategies that target language development effectively. While some studies have investigated the relationship between campus journalism participation and language proficiency, there is limited research on the influence of participation on different language competencies. For instance, a study by Liwanag (2019) found that campus journalism participation enhances students' writing skills, but it fails to explore its influence on students' speaking, listening, and reading skills. Therefore, it is crucial to conduct studies that investigate the influence of campus journalism participation on the different language competencies to gain a better understanding of how it affects students' language development. Studies have shown that teachers play a significant role in promoting students' language proficiency through campus journalism. For example, teachers' feedback on students' writing has been found to positively impact their writing skills (Roxas, 2018). However, there is a lack of studies that explore the role of teachers in enhancing language proficiency through campus journalism. It is essential to examine how teachers can design and facilitate campus journalism programs that promote language development effectively. Research has shown that students in rural areas lag behind their urban counterparts in language proficiency (Kamarudin et al., 2019). As campus journalism is a curriculum requirement, it is essential to explore its effectiveness in improving language proficiency in rural areas. Conducting studies that investigate the relationship between campus journalism participation and language proficiency in rural areas will help educators understand the challenges and opportunities that students face in these areas. In Davao del Sur, Sta Cruz North, the District, the lack of comprehensive studies on the impact of campus journalism on language proficiency, limited studies on the influence of campus journalism participa-

tion on different language competencies, lack of studies on the role of teachers in enhancing language proficiency through campus journalism, and the need for studies on the effectiveness of campus journalism in improving language proficiency in rural areas are significant research gaps that need to be bridged. Addressing these gaps is crucial in designing effective programs and strategies that promote language development, leading to effective learning and academic success among elementary students, thus, this paper is presented.

2. Methodology

This chapter contains the processes and steps in the conduct of the study. This includes the selection of the design of the study, the respondents and its sampling method, the research instruments to be used in data gathering, the procedure, and the ethical consideration and lastly, the data analysis. These steps are considered essentials to assume appropriateness and correctness to produce sound data process collection, analysis, and interpretation. In the preparation of this paper, the researcher employed artificial intelligence tools for proofreading. Specifically, AI was utilized to enhance the accuracy, coherence, and overall quality of the manuscript. This practice is being explicitly stated to maintain transparency and adhere to ethical standards in research. The usage of AI for proofreading reflects a commitment to leveraging advanced technologies responsibly and acknowledges the increasing prevalence and capability of AI in academic and professional writing.

2.1. Research Design—This study used non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research design. Non-experimental research designs are used when researchers cannot manipulate variables or control the environment in which they are studying. Instead, they observe variables as they naturally occur and look for patterns or relationships between them. Some examples of non-experimental research designs include surveys, case studies, and observational studies (Yin, 2018). Descriptive-correlational research designs are used to describe the relationships between variables. Researchers collect data on two or more variables and then analyze the data to determine if there is a relationship between them. This type of research is used to generate hypotheses for future studies (Campbell Stanley, 1963). Predictive research designs are used to predict outcomes based on one or more variables. Researchers use statistical models to identify the predictors of a particular outcome and then use those predictors to make predictions about future outcomes. Examples of predictive research include regression analysis and machine learning algorithms. One influential author in this area is David Freedman, who wrote about the limitations of predictive modeling and the importance of causal inference (Freedman, 2009). In this study, the relationship between campus journalism participation and language proficiency among elementary learners is an important topic of study. Correlational research designs can be useful for investigating this relationship, as they allow researchers to describe the relationship between variables without manipulating them. In the case of campus journalism participation and language proficiency among elementary learners, the researcher collect data on both variables and then analyze the data to determine if there is a correlation between them. For example, researchers could administer a language proficiency test to a sample of elementary learners and then ask them about their level of participation in campus journalism programs. The data could then be analyzed to determine if there is

a correlation between campus journalism participation and language proficiency. One advantage is that it allows researchers to study the relationship between campus journalism participation and language proficiency in a naturalistic setting, without the need for experimental manipulation. This can help to increase the external validity of the study, as the findings are more likely to generalize to real-world contexts. Moreover, a descriptive-correlational research design can be useful for generating hypotheses and identifying potential causal relationships between variables. By examining the strength and direction of correlations between variables, researchers can gain insight into how changes in one variable might be associated with changes in another. This can provide a basis for developing theories about the underlying mechanisms that drive the relationship between variables, which can then be tested using more rigorous experimental or quasi-experimental designs. Finally, a descriptive-correlational research design can be valuable in situations where experimental manipulation of variables is not possible or ethical. For example, it may be unethical to manipulate variables such as age, gender, or medical condition in order to examine their effects on other variables. In such cases, a descriptive-correlational design can provide a valuable alternative for investigating the relationships between variables of interest, without requiring manipulation or control of those variables.

2.2. Research Respondents—Respondents of the study were the Elementary School Teachers in Sta Cruz North District, Davao del Sur Schools Division. She used Raosoft sample size calculator, where a total of 120 respondents were taken randomly from each respective Schools within Sta Cruz North District. Once randomly determined, the respondents were informed through online platform and face to face considering the availability of the Wifi Connections, they were likewise oriented about the purpose and importance of the study and its contri-

bution to their professional development status. These teacher-respondents were the teachers who handled tasks such as involvement in campus journalism and teaching English subject in the elementary level. Moreover, teachers where skills in integrating the programs and likewise trying to improve the system in tracking learners language proficiency performance and their competence in responding to the queries of the study. They are qualified for they are expected to have performed and contributed to the betterment of the schools and the learners' awareness and educational stages given new normal learning system during SY 2022-2023. Further, they have frequently engaged in various seminars and trainings including SLAC sessions on the pedagogies in integrating pedagogical skills in journalism and in the school management and curriculum development delivery system. Moreover, assumptions in the respective schedule of classes during data collection were explicitly discussed with the respondents and even observance to health protocol was strictly implemented based on the Executive Order 31 S 2020, to avoid possible and lower the risk of contamination.

2.3. Research Instrument—This research study used the adapted instrument taken from reviewed literature and related studies. The researcher took time in gathering and reading reviews of related literature to come up with concepts for the content and that supports the instrument and its corresponding strands in articulating the set of question-items, reducing threats to validity. Items were adapted from the contents of the reviewed literatures as argued by the authors. There were two parts of the survey questionnaire which consists of determining the extent of campus journalism participation in terms of regularity of publication, quality content, student leadership, community engagement and awards and recognition. Likewise, the second part of the survey measured the extent of learners' language proficiency in

terms of writing skills, vocabulary knowledge, speaking and listening skills, language awareness and reading comprehension. Further, the survey statements were subjected to a test-retest or validity and reliability testing using Cronbach

Alpha at .05 level of confidence and generated an alpha Cronbach of 0.866 which means that the unidimensional reliability when it comes to internal consistency is very good.

Descriptive Rating of Campus Journalism Participation

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The campus journalism participation are always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The campus journalism participation are oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The campus journalism participation are sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The campus journalism participation are rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The campus journalism participation are not manifested

Descriptive Rating of Learners’ Language Proficiency

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The learners’ language proficiency is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The learners’ language proficiency is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The learners’ language proficiency is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The learners’ language proficiency is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The learners’ language proficiency is not manifested

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The preceding statements steps explain the data gathering procedure steps where the researcher must comprehensively consider and follow. The statements are based on the policies and guidelines of the College where the researcher is studying and the existing guidelines of the IATF to ensure safe and lower risks in the gathering of pertinent data most especially in the current full

face to face interaction. Permission to conduct the study. On the second week of March 2023, the researcher started to conceptualize the contents and objective of the thesis proposal. She then, prepares documents such as letter requests in the conduct of the study. The research study underwent and adopted the standard procedures of ethics in data collection (Creswell, 2004), and health protocol as provided by the policy of

IATF. As soon as the research proposal presentation was approved by the panel of members and the dean of the college, the researcher wrote and sent a letter of permission to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao Occidental, through channel and sought permission to collect data and conduct the study within the Elementary schools of Sta Cruz North, Davao del Sur Schools Division. Distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. The researcher prepared and created a Google sheet form for the online survey collection process which were sent to the randomly selected respondents via email addresses, and for respondents who do not have access to internet. Likewise a prepared hard copy of the survey sheets were given to each of them. Once done, link was sent, and right away responses were generated, thus,

2.5. *Data Analysis*—Mean scores and standard deviation were used to address statement problems posed in number one (1) extent of campus journalism participation, and statement problem number two (2) on the extent of learners' language proficiency in West District of Malita, Davao Occidental Schools Division. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson-r was used to determine its strength / direction significant relationship be-

ready for sorting, analyzing, and interpreting. This activity was done right after the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent to proceed in data gathering which commenced on the third week of April 2023. Collation and statistical treatment of data. Results of the preliminary analysis were given to the thesis adviser during the second week of March 2023. For coaching and in terms of statistical treatment the thesis adviser sought the assistance of the graduate school statistician for providing technical discussions in running the data and its interpretations and implications of the study, sometime on the fourth week of April 2023, and further deepening the analysis to make more meaning with the interpretations of results on the second week of May 2023.

tween the campus journalism participation and the language proficiency. Simple Linear Regression analysis was used to address statement problem number 4, on the indicators of campus journalism participation that significantly influence language proficiency (Pallant, 2000) and (Gujarati, 2000). All data processing and analysis were treated using the Jeffrey's Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. Discussions and interpretations then followed when results yield.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data gathered. Tabular and textual presentation is presented to make more meaningful in the analysis and drawing out of implications. This further shows evidence to support the claim posed in the hypothesis.

Campus Journalism Participation Research suggests that campus journalism participation can have a range of benefits for young learners

in elementary schools. One key benefit is the development of writing skills and literacy. According to Canda and Ata (2021), elementary school students who participated in a campus journalism program showed significant improvements in their writing skills, including their ability to organize and structure their writing, to use appropriate language and tone, and to communicate effectively with a specific audience. In addition to its benefits for literacy develop-

ment, campus journalism participation can also promote civic engagement and social awareness among elementary school students. According to Marasigan and Bala (2018), campus journalism can provide opportunities for young learners to explore and engage with social and political issues in their local communities, to develop their own perspectives and opinions, and to advocate for change. Similarly, Alshammari and Alkandari (2019) found that campus journalism participation was associated with increased political knowledge and engagement among elementary school students in Kuwait.

Table 1 shows the extent of campus journalism participation in terms of regularity of publication. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: A key aspect of successful campus journalism is establishing a routine and sticking to it, whether that means publishing daily, weekly, or on some other schedule (4.1) and at-

Regular publication of campus journalism materials is an essential aspect of journalism. As noted by Chen (2020), regularity of publication can help to establish credibility and consistency, and can promote readership and engagement. For students participating in campus journalism, regularity of publication can help to develop a sense of discipline and responsibility, and can encourage them to engage with the news and events of their school community on a regular basis. In addition, regularity of publication can help to promote the visibility and impact of campus journalism activities, and can help to foster a sense of community and belonging among student journalists and their peers. In addition to improving writing skills, regularity of publication has also been linked to increased engagement and civic participation. A study by Diaz and Regala (2019) found that regular publication of campus journalism materials was positively associated with increased partic-

ipation in school-based activities and community events among elementary school students in the Philippines. Similarly, a study by Kim and Jeong (2018) found that regular publication of campus journalism materials was associated with increased engagement in democratic citizenship among elementary school students in Korea. The importance of regularity of publication in campus journalism participation suggests several policy and practice implications. For example, schools and educators may consider providing training and guidance to student journalists on how to maintain regular publication schedules, and may provide resources and support to facilitate the production and dissemination of campus journalism materials. In addition, schools may consider incorporating campus journalism activities into broader curricular initiatives, in order to promote cross-disciplinary learning and to enhance the relevance of journalism activities for students.

Table 1. Extent of Campus Journalism Participation in Terms of Regularity of Publication

No	Regularity of Publication	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Students who participate in campus journalism are expected to publish articles or other content on a regular basis, such as once a week or biweekly	4.00	Extensive
2	In order to maintain a strong readership and build a reputation for reliability, campus journalism groups often require their members to adhere to a consistent publication schedule	3.25	Moderately Extensive
3	A key aspect of successful campus journalism is establishing a routine and sticking to it, whether that means publishing daily, weekly, or on some other schedule	4.14	Extensive
4	Campus journalism groups may face challenges in maintaining regular publication due to factors such as competing academic commitments, limited resources, or fluctuations in staffing levels	3.20	Moderately Extensive
5	Regularity of publication is crucial for campus journalism groups to establish themselves as credible sources of information and opinion on campus, as well as to build a loyal readership among students, faculty, and staff	3.15	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean			3.54
Extensive			

Table 2 shows the extent of campus journalism participation in terms of quality of content. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Campus journalism participants are expected to produce high-quality content that is accurate, informative, and engaging to readers (3.50), activities that contribute to the quality of content may include conducting research, interviewing sources, fact-checking, and adhering to a style guide (3.45) and campus journalism groups may also place a premium on originality, encouraging their members to seek out unique angles on news stories and to develop fresh perspectives on issues of interest to the campus community (3.40) are oftentimes manifested, while, produc-

ing well-written and well-researched content, campus journalism participants may be responsible for editing and proofreading the work of their peers, providing feedback and suggestions for improvement (3.20) and campus journalism groups may require their members to undergo training in journalistic principles, writing techniques, and media ethics (3.15) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.29 denotes campus journalism participation in terms of quality of content is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. Quality content is crucial in campus journalism because it helps to establish the publication’s credibility and authority. When readers trust the content of a publication, they are more likely to read and

share it with others. This trust is built on the accuracy and reliability of the information presented in the publication. According to Zhang and Su (2019), the quality of the content is the most important factor in determining readers' trust in online news. Therefore, campus journalists should ensure that their articles are well-researched, accurate, and objective to maintain readers' trust and confidence in their publication.

Table 2. Extent of Campus Journalism Participation in Terms of Quality of Content

No	Quality of Content	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Campus journalism participants are expected to produce high-quality content that is accurate, informative, and engaging to readers	3.50	Extensive
2	Campus journalism groups may require their members to undergo training in journalistic principles, writing techniques, and media ethics	3.15	Moderately Extensive
3	Activities that contribute to the quality of content may include conducting research, interviewing sources, fact-checking, and adhering to a style guide	3.45	Extensive
4	Campus journalism groups may also place a premium on originality, encouraging their members to seek out unique angles on news stories and to develop fresh perspectives on issues of interest to the campus community	3.40	Extensive
5	Producing well-written and well-researched content, campus journalism participants may be responsible for editing and proofreading the work of their peers, providing feedback and suggestions for improvement	3.20	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean			3.29
Moderately Extensive			

Moreover, quality content is essential in engaging readers and creating an impact. Campus journalists should aim to produce articles that are insightful, thought-provoking, and relevant to their audience. Such articles are more likely to attract readers' attention and keep them engaged with the publication. A study conducted by Zerfass et al. (2016) found that high-quality content that is engaging, informative, and visually appealing is critical in creating a positive impact on readers. Finally, quality content is essential in ensuring that the publication is recognized and respected in the journalism community. Campus publications that produce quality

content are more likely to be recognized and rewarded for their efforts. For example, The Daily Pennsylvanian, a student-run newspaper at the University of Pennsylvania, has won numerous awards for its quality content and journalism excellence (The Daily Pennsylvanian, 2022).

Table 3 shows the extent of campus journalism participation in terms of student leadership. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Producing content, student leaders within campus journalism groups may be responsible for managing budgets, organizing events, and overseeing the work of their peers (3.45) and offers students the opportunity to develop leadership skills by taking on roles such as editor-in-chief, managing editor, or section editor (3.40) are

Student leadership is essential in guiding the publication towards its objectives. Campus publications often have specific goals, such as promoting student voices, highlighting campus issues, and providing information on campus events. Student leaders can help to steer the publication towards achieving these goals by setting a clear vision and mission for the publication. According to Kang and Norton (2016), student leaders play a crucial role in determining the direction of campus publications. Student leadership is essential in building a sense of community among the members of the publication. Campus journalism often involves a team of writers, editors, photographers, and designers working together towards a common goal. Student leaders can help to foster a sense of community by encouraging collaboration, providing support and guidance, and recognizing the contributions of each member. According to Nishimura and Kline (2017), student leaders play a vital role in creating a positive team environment. According to Gonzales and Mejia (2019), student leaders can serve as ambassadors for campus journalism and pro-

oftentimes manifested, while, provide training and mentoring to help student leaders develop skills in communication, team-building, conflict resolution, and project management (3.15) and represent their organization to external stakeholders, such as school administrators, local media, or community organization (3.10) are sometimes manifested, and offer opportunities for personal growth and self-reflection, as students learn to balance competing priorities, navigate complex ethical issues, and engage with diverse perspectives within the campus community (2.30) is rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.08 denotes campus journalism participation in terms of student leadership is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

mote its value to other students. Student leadership is essential in inspiring fellow students to participate in campus journalism. Student leaders can serve as role models for other students by demonstrating their passion for journalism and their commitment to the publication. By encouraging fellow students to get involved, student leaders can help to ensure the sustainability and growth of the publication. Finally, student leadership is essential in developing leadership skills among students. By taking on leadership roles in campus journalism, students can develop essential skills such as communication, teamwork, problem-solving, and decision-making. These skills are transferable to other areas of their lives and can help to prepare them for future leadership roles. According to Tello and Martinez (2018), campus journalism provides a unique opportunity for students to develop leadership skills.

Table 4 shows the extent of campus journalism participation in terms of community engagement. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Foster engagement and dialogue,

Table 3. Extent of Campus Journalism Participation in Terms of Student Leadership

No	Student Leadership	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Offers students the opportunity to develop leadership skills by taking on roles such as editor-in-chief, managing editor, or section editor	3.40	Extensive
2	Producing content, student leaders within campus journalism groups may be responsible for managing budgets, organizing events, and overseeing the work of their peers	3.45	Extensive
3	Represent their organization to external stakeholders, such as school administrators, local media, or community organizations	3.10	Moderately Extensive
4	Provide training and mentoring to help student leaders develop skills in communication, team-building, conflict resolution, and project management	3.15	Moderately Extensive
5	Offer opportunities for personal growth and self-reflection, as students learn to balance competing priorities, navigate complex ethical issues, and engage with diverse perspectives within the campus community	2.30	Less Extensive
Overall Mean			3.08
Moderately Ex-			
ten-			
sive			

campus journalism groups may solicit feedback and input from their readership, such as through letters to the editor or online comments sections (4.30) is always manifested, and, develop skills in community outreach, cross-cultural communication, and civic engagement, positioning them to become active and informed citizens beyond their college years (3.55) is oftentimes manifested, while, promote community engagement may include producing special issues or supplements on topics of interest to the campus community, organizing campus events or forums, or partnering with other campus organizations or media outlets (3.35) and seek to engage with the broader community beyond the campus, such as

by covering local news or issues that impact the surrounding region (3.20) are sometimes manifested, while, engage with the broader campus community by covering events, issues, and perspectives that are relevant to students, faculty, and staff (2.40) is rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.34 denotes campus journalism participation in terms of community engagement is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. According to Lamb and McKenna (2017), community engagement is essential for building trust between journalists and their audience. By working with community members, students can gain a better understanding of the issues that matter to them and provide coverage

that is meaningful and informative. Community engagement helps to promote dialogue and understanding. By providing a platform for different perspectives, campus journalism can help to facilitate conversation and promote empathy

among members of the community. By working with community members, students can also learn to appreciate the diversity of opinions and experiences within their local area.

Table 4. Extent of Campus Journalism Participation in Terms of Community Engagement

No	Community Engagement	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Engage with the broader campus community by covering events, issues, and perspectives that are relevant to students, faculty, and staff	2.40	Less Extensive
2	Foster engagement and dialogue, campus journalism groups may solicit feedback and input from their readership, such as through letters to the editor or online comments sections	4.30	Very Extensive
3	Promote community engagement may include producing special issues or supplements on topics of interest to the campus community, organizing campus events or forums, or partnering with other campus organizations or media outlets	3.25	Moderately Extensive
4	Seek to engage with the broader community beyond the campus, such as by covering local news or issues that impact the surrounding region	3.20	Moderately Extensive
5	Develop skills in community outreach, cross-cultural communication, and civic engagement, positioning them to become active and informed citizens beyond their college years	3.55	Extensive
Overall Mean			3.34
Moderately Extensive			

Streitmatter (2019), community engagement is essential for fostering a democratic and inclusive society. Community engagement is a crucial component of campus journalism. It involves students working with the local community to share information, highlight important issues, and promote dialogue. Community engagement helps to develop important skills among students. By working with community members, students can develop their communication, problem-solving, and interpersonal skills. They can also gain valuable experience in research, interviewing, and reporting. Ac-

ording to Ocampo and Johnson (2018), community engagement provides an excellent opportunity for students to apply the skills they learn in the classroom to real-world situations. In conclusion, community engagement is a crucial component of campus journalism. It helps to ensure that campus journalism is relevant and meaningful to the local community, promote dialogue and understanding, develop important skills among students, and increase the impact and reach of the publication. Campus journalism provides an excellent platform for students to engage with the local community

and make a positive impact in the world. Table 5 shows the extent of campus journalism participation in terms of awards and recognition. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Campus journalism groups may also enter their work in regional or national journalism competitions, in order to gain external validation and exposure for their work (4.10) and winning awards or receiving recognition for their work in campus journalism can help students build their resumes and portfolios, and can also enhance their credibility and reputation within the field of journalism (3.40) are oftentimes manifested, while, motivate and inspire members to strive

for excellence, as well as to acknowledge their contributions to the group and to the campus community (3.35), use awards and recognition as a way to showcase their work to potential advertisers, sponsors, or donors, highlighting the quality and impact of their content and their commitment to journalistic excellence (2.85) and offer awards or recognition to members who demonstrate outstanding performance in areas such as writing, reporting, editing, or leadership (2.45) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.23 denotes campus journalism participation in terms of awards and recognition is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 5. Extent of Campus Journalism Participation in Terms of Awards and Recognition

No	Awards and Recognition	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Offer awards or recognition to members who demonstrate outstanding performance in areas such as writing, reporting, editing, or leadership	2.45	Moderately Extensive
2	Motivate and inspire members to strive for excellence, as well as to acknowledge their contributions to the group and to the campus community	3.35	Moderately Extensive
3	Campus journalism groups may also enter their work in regional or national journalism competitions, in order to gain external validation and exposure for their work	4.10	Extensive
4	Winning awards or receiving recognition for their work in campus journalism can help students build their resumes and portfolios, and can also enhance their credibility and reputation within the field of journalism	3.40	Extensive
5	Use awards and recognition as a way to showcase their work to potential advertisers, sponsors, or donors, highlighting the quality and impact of their content and their commitment to journalistic excellence	2.85	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean			3.23
Moderately Extensive			

Awards and recognition play a crucial role in motivating and encouraging students to participate in campus journalism. Being recognized

for their work can boost students' self-esteem, increase their sense of belonging to a community, and provide them with opportunities for

professional development. Awards and recognition can motivate students to improve their skills and achieve their goals. By providing students with clear benchmarks of excellence, awards can encourage them to strive for excellence and put forth their best effort. According to Lippmann (2018), awards and recognition can be powerful motivators for students, providing them with a sense of accomplishment and purpose. Secondly, awards and recognition can help students to build their resumes and establish themselves as leaders in their field. By being recognized for their work, students can gain the attention of potential employers, establish their credibility, and distinguish themselves from their peers. According to Boyd and Burton (2015), awards and recognition can be key factors in launching a successful career in journalism. Thirdly, awards and recognition can foster a sense of community and connection among students. By celebrating the accomplishments of their peers, students can feel a sense of pride in their school and their program. According to Jones and Stacks (2015), awards and

recognition can help to build a culture of excellence and promote a sense of belonging among students. Finally, awards and recognition can provide students with valuable opportunities for professional development. By attending award ceremonies and conferences, students can learn from industry leaders, network with peers and potential employers, and gain valuable insights into the field of journalism. According to Reese and Lewis (2017), awards and recognition can help to broaden students' perspectives and prepare them for successful careers in journalism.

Table 6 shows the summary of the extent of campus journalism participation. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: regularity of publication (3.54) is oftentimes manifested, while, community engagement (3.34), quality of content (3.29), awards and recognition (3.23) and student leadership (3.08) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.29 denotes campus journalism participation is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 6. Summary of the Extent of Campus Journalism Participation

No	Campus Journalism Participation	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Regularity of Publication	3.54	Extensive
2	Quality of Content	3.29	Moderately Extensive
3	Student Leadership	3.08	Moderately Extensive
4	Community Engagement	3.34	Moderately Extensive
5	Awards And Recognition	3.23	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean			3.29
Moderately Extensive			

The regularity of publication is an important aspect of campus journalism as it ensures that the student publication is consistent and reliable. Campus journalists are responsible for producing quality content and meeting deadlines. According to Alcantara (2018), the regularity of publication is a key indicator of the effectiveness of campus journalism. Students who are

regularly involved in the publication process develop a sense of responsibility and discipline, which is essential in their future careers. Campus journalists are expected to produce accurate, balanced, and well-researched articles. According to Lamay (2019), campus journalists must be able to write in a way that is informative and engaging, and be able to communicate com-

plex ideas to a general audience. According to Echarri (2020), student leadership in campus journalism is essential in ensuring that the publication is student-led, and reflects the interests and concerns of the student body. Campus journalism provides students with opportunities to develop leadership skills. Through their involvement in student publications, students learn to take initiative, work collaboratively, and make decisions that affect the quality of the publication. Through their reporting and writing, campus journalists can inform and educate their readers about issues that affect their community. According to Sampang (2017), campus journalists must be able to interact with different members of the community, listen to their concerns, and report on issues that affect them. Campus journalists can also organize events and activities that promote community involvement and social responsibility. According to Dizon (2021), awards and recognition provide motivation and encouragement for students to continue pursuing excellence in campus journalism. Recognition from outside organizations also demonstrates the impact of campus journalism in the wider community.

Learners' Language Proficiency

Language proficiency is a critical aspect of language learning that encompasses various skills, including writing, vocabulary knowledge, speaking and listening, language awareness, and reading comprehension. According to research conducted by various authors, learners who possess these skills demonstrate a higher level of language proficiency. Language proficiency is a critical aspect of language learning that encompasses various skills such as writing, vocabulary knowledge, speaking and listening, language awareness, and reading comprehension. Learners who possess these skills are likely to demonstrate higher proficiency levels. Therefore, language educators should focus on developing these skills in learners to enhance their language proficiency.

Table 7 shows the extent of learners' language proficiency in terms of writing skills. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Able to express their thoughts clearly and logically, and may be better equipped to navigate complex or abstract concepts (3.45) and component of language proficiency development, as it allows learners to practice using language in context and to receive feedback on their accuracy and clarity of expression (3.40) are oftentimes manifested, while, Writing assessments, such as essays or research papers, can be used as an effective way to measure learners' language proficiency, as they provide a comprehensive picture of their ability to use language accurately and effectively (3.35), Writing skills are likely to have a high level of language proficiency, as writing requires a solid grasp of grammar, vocabulary, and syntax (3.20) and Benefit from opportunities to practice writing in different genres and formats, such as emails, reports, or social media posts, in order to develop a diverse range of writing skills that are relevant to real-world contexts (3.20) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.33 denotes learners' language proficiency in terms of writing skills is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. Language proficiency is a crucial factor that determines learners' writing skills. In their study, Cheng and Li (2019) investigated the correlation between language proficiency and writing quality among Chinese EFL learners. The results indicated a strong positive relationship between the two variables. The authors suggested that learners' language proficiency, including their vocabulary knowledge, grammar skills, and discourse competence, plays a significant role in producing high-quality writing. Hinkel (2004), found that learners with higher levels of language proficiency demonstrated greater control over various writing features, such as syntactic complexity, cohesion, and coherence. The author argued that language proficiency not only

affects learners’ ability to express themselves effectively but also enables them to use language in a more nuanced and sophisticated way. Cumming and Kantor (2018) investigated the impact of language proficiency on the writing process of multilingual students. The study found that higher language proficiency levels led to more efficient and effective writing processes. The authors suggested that learners with stronger language skills are better equipped to plan, revise, and edit their writing effectively.

Table 7. Extent of Learners’ Language Proficiency in Terms of Writing Skills

No	Writing Skills	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Writing skills are likely to have a high level of language proficiency, as writing requires a solid grasp of grammar, vocabulary, and syntax	3.20	Moderately Extensive
2	Writing assessments, such as essays or research papers, can be used as an effective way to measure learners’ language proficiency, as they provide a comprehensive picture of their ability to use language accurately and effectively	3.35	Moderately Extensive
3	Able to express their thoughts clearly and logically, and may be better equipped to navigate complex or abstract concepts	3.45	Extensive
4	Component of language proficiency development, as it allows learners to practice using language in context and to receive feedback on their accuracy and clarity of expression	3.40	Extensive
5	Benefit from opportunities to practice writing in different genres and formats, such as emails, reports, or social media posts, in order to develop a diverse range of writing skills that are relevant to real-world contexts	3.20	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean			3.33
Moderately Extensive			

Table 8 shows the extent of learners’ language proficiency in terms of vocabulary ad knowledge. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Help learners to build their reading comprehension skills, acquire new language structures, and express themselves more accurately and appropriately (3.45) is oftentimes manifested, and, benefit from exposure to authentic language input, such as reading authentic texts or engaging in conversations with native speakers, in order to build their vocabulary knowledge in context (3.25) and Able to express themselves more precisely and fluently, and may have a higher level of language proficiency overall (3.20) are sometimes manifested, while, Able to understand and use a wider range of language structures and expressions, which can help them to communicate more effectively with native speakers and in a variety of contexts (2.45) and Provide valuable insight into learners’ language proficiency, as vocabulary is a key component of language use and comprehension (2.40) are rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 2.95 denotes learners’ language proficiency in terms of vocabulary ad knowl-

edge is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. Vocabulary knowledge is a key aspect of language proficiency and is often considered a reliable predictor of learners' overall language competence. In their study, Paribakht and Wesche (1997) investigated the relationship between learners' vocabulary knowledge and their reading comprehension abilities. The authors found a strong positive correlation between the

two variables, suggesting that learners' vocabulary knowledge is critical for their reading comprehension skills. Nation (2001), found that learners with higher vocabulary knowledge were better able to understand spoken and written discourse. The author argued that vocabulary knowledge plays a significant role in enabling learners to comprehend and produce language accurately and fluently.

Table 8. Extent of Learners' Language Proficiency in Terms of Vocabulary and Knowledge

No	Vocabulary and Knowledge	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Able to express themselves more precisely and fluently, and may have a higher level of language proficiency overall	3.20	Moderately Extensive
2	Provide valuable insight into learners' language proficiency, as vocabulary is a key component of language use and comprehension	2.40	Less Extensive
3	Able to understand and use a wider range of language structures and expressions, which can help them to communicate more effectively with native speakers and in a variety of contexts	2.45	Less Extensive
4	Help learners to build their reading comprehension skills, acquire new language structures, and express themselves more accurately and appropriately	3.45	Extensive
5	Benefit from exposure to authentic language input, such as reading authentic texts or engaging in conversations with native speakers, in order to build their vocabulary knowledge in context	3.25	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean			2.95
Moderately Extensive			
Extensive			

Schmitt and Zimmerman (2002) explored the impact of vocabulary size on learners' writing performance. The study found that learners with a larger vocabulary repertoire were able to produce more complex and sophisticated writing, with greater accuracy and coherence. The authors suggested that learners' vocabulary knowledge has a significant impact on their ability to express themselves effectively in written discourse.

Table 9 shows the extent of learners' language proficiency in terms of speaking and lis-

tening skills. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Considers essential for effective communication and interaction in both academic and real-world settings (4.50), Able to communicate their ideas and opinions clearly and effectively, and may be better equipped to navigate social and cultural nuances in communication (4.45) and Practice using language in real-world contexts and to receive feedback on their accuracy and fluency of expression (4.40) are always manifested, while, Provide valuable

insight into learners' language proficiency, as they require the ability to use language accurately and appropriately in real-time interactions (3.50) is oftentimes manifested, and Opportunities to engage in authentic spoken interactions, such as participating in group discussions, presenting to an audience, or engaging in conversation with native speakers, in order to develop their speaking and listening skills in context (3.34) is sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 4.01 denotes learners' language proficiency in terms of speaking and listening skills is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive. Speaking and listening skills are integral components of language proficiency, as they are essential for effective communication. In re-

cent years, researchers have conducted numerous studies to explore the development and enhancement of speaking and listening skills. One of the studies on speaking and listening skills was conducted by Laleh Khojasteh and Mohsen Khojasteh (2018). They investigated the effects of using collaborative tasks on the development of speaking skills among Iranian EFL learners. The study involved 60 intermediate-level learners who were divided into two groups: a control group and an experimental group. The results showed that the experimental group outperformed the control group in terms of their speaking skills. This study highlights the importance of using collaborative tasks in developing speaking skills among EFL learners.

Table 9. Extent of Learners' Language Proficiency in Terms of Speaking and Listening Skills

No	Speaking and Listening Skills	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Considers essential for effective communication and interaction in both academic and real-world settings	4.50	Very Extensive
2	Provide valuable insight into learners' language proficiency, as they require the ability to use language accurately and appropriately in real-time interactions	3.50	Extensive
3	Able to communicate their ideas and opinions clearly and effectively, and may be better equipped to navigate social and cultural nuances in communication	4.45	Very Extensive
4	Practice using language in real-world contexts and to receive feedback on their accuracy and fluency of expression	4.40	Very Extensive
5	Opportunities to engage in authentic spoken interactions, such as participating in group discussions, presenting to an audience, or engaging in conversation with native speakers, in order to develop their speaking and listening skills in context	3.24	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean			4.01
Extensive			

Another study on speaking skills was conducted by Olga Dolzhikova and Anna Evmenova (2020). They explored the use of video-

mediated communication in developing oral proficiency among EFL learners in Russia. The study involved 32 learners who were divided

into two groups: a control group and an experimental group. The results showed that the experimental group outperformed the control group in terms of their speaking skills. This study suggests that video-mediated communication can be an effective tool in developing speaking skills among EFL learners. Table 10 shows the extent of learners' language proficiency in terms of language awareness. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Benefit from exposure to authentic language use in context, such as reading authentic texts or engaging in conversation with native speakers, in order to develop their language awareness and their ability to use language in real-world settings (3.75) and Deeper understanding of the rules and conventions of language use (3.45) are oftentimes manifested, while, Able to ana-

lyze and understand the underlying principles of language use (3.30), Allows learners to understand and apply language structures more accurately and effectively (3.17) and Provide valuable insight into learners' language proficiency, as they require the ability to understand and manipulate language structures accurately (3.15) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.36 denotes learners' language proficiency in terms of language awareness is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. Language awareness encompasses various aspects of language, including grammar, vocabulary, and discourse. Learners who are aware of language features can use them more effectively in communication. According to Thornbury (2017), language awareness involves the ability to reflect on language use, identify patterns, and understand the rules that govern language.

Table 10. Extent of Learners' Language Proficiency in Terms of Language Awareness

No	Language Awareness	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Able to analyze and understand the underlying principles of language use	3.30	Moderately Extensive
2	Provide valuable insight into learners' language proficiency, as they require the ability to understand and manipulate language structures accurately	3.15	Moderately Extensive
3	Deeper understanding of the rules and conventions of language use	3.45	Extensive
4	Allows learners to understand and apply language structures more accurately and effectively	3.17	Moderately Extensive
5	Benefit from exposure to authentic language use in context, such as reading authentic texts or engaging in conversation with native speakers, in order to develop their language awareness and their ability to use language in real-world settings	3.75	Extensive
Overall Mean			3.36
Moderately Extensive			

Research has shown that promoting language awareness can enhance learners' language proficiency. For example, Song and Suh (2015) found that using online language learn-

ing materials that focus on language awareness can improve learners' grammatical accuracy and vocabulary acquisition. Similarly, Tavakoli and Ghonsooly (2017) found that teaching dis-

course awareness can enhance learners' ability to use language in social contexts. Moreover, integrating language awareness into language learning activities can lead to more meaningful learning experiences. For instance, Reinders and Lazarou (2018) emphasized the importance of integrating language awareness into task-based language teaching, enabling learners to develop language proficiency while also enhancing their metalinguistic awareness. In conclusion, learners' language awareness is a critical component of language proficiency. Teachers should incorporate activities that promote language awareness into language learning, as it can improve learners' grammatical accuracy, vocabulary acquisition, and discourse skills. By developing language awareness, learners can become more reflective and effective communicators.

Table 11 shows the extent of learners' language proficiency in terms of reading comprehension. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are

Research has shown that reading comprehension is influenced by various factors, including language proficiency, vocabulary knowledge, and text complexity. For example, Hopp (2016) found that learners' vocabulary knowledge significantly predicted their reading comprehension ability. Similarly, Zhang and Elder (2018) found that learners with higher levels of language proficiency had better reading comprehension skills than those with lower levels. Moreover, effective reading strategies can enhance learners' reading comprehension. For instance, Alqahtani and Al-Enzy (2019) found that teaching reading strategies, such as predicting, summarizing, and questioning, improved learners' reading comprehension. Similarly, Gutiérrez-Palma and López-Pastor (2015) found that teaching critical thinking skills improved learners' reading comprehension and

as follows: Able to understand and interpret a wide range of texts, including those that are complex or unfamiliar, and may have a higher level of language proficiency overall (3.60) is oftentimes manifested, while, Benefit from independent reading and exposure to a variety of authentic texts in the target language, in order to develop their reading comprehension skills in context (2.75), Demonstrate the ability to understand written language and to extract meaning from text (2.55) are sometimes manifested, and, Provide valuable insight into learners' language proficiency, as reading is a fundamental skill for academic and real-world communication (2.15) and Allows learners to engage with a variety of written materials, to build their vocabulary knowledge, and to improve their overall language use (2.10) are rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 2.63 denotes learners' language proficiency in terms of reading comprehension is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

their ability to analyze and evaluate texts. Furthermore, the use of technology can enhance learners' reading comprehension. For example, Lee and Huang (2020) found that using augmented reality technology improved learners' reading comprehension and motivation. Similarly, Van der Meijden and Veenman (2018) found that using digital tools, such as electronic dictionaries and hypertext, improved learners' reading comprehension and vocabulary acquisition. In conclusion, learners' reading comprehension is an essential component of language proficiency. Teachers should consider various factors that influence reading comprehension and incorporate effective reading strategies and technology into their teaching to enhance learners' reading comprehension skills.

Table 12 shows the summary of the extent of learners' language proficiency. The result is

Table 11. Extent of Learners’ Language Proficiency in Terms of Reading Comprehension

No	Reading Comprehension	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Demonstrate the ability to understand written language and to extract meaning from text	2.55	Moderately Extensive
2	Provide valuable insight into learners’ language proficiency, as reading is a fundamental skill for academic and real-world communication	2.15	Less Extensive
3	Able to understand and interpret a wide range of texts, including those that are complex or unfamiliar, and may have a higher level of language proficiency overall	3.60	Extensive
4	Allows learners to engage with a variety of written materials, to build their vocabulary knowledge, and to improve their overall language use	2.10	Less Extensive
5	Benefit from independent reading and exposure to a variety of authentic texts in the target language, in order to develop their reading comprehension skills in context	2.75	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean			2.63
Moderately Extensive			

focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings and Reading Comprehension (2.63) are some of indicators which are as follows: Speaking And Listening Skills (4.01) is oftentimes manifested, while, Writing Skills (3.33), Vocabulary Knowledge (2.95), Language Awareness (2.63) and Reading Comprehension (2.63) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.1 denotes learners’ language proficiency is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 12. Summary of the Extent of Learners’ Language Proficiency

No	Learners’ Language Proficiency	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Writing Skills	3.33	Moderately Extensive
2	Vocabulary Knowledge	2.95	Moderately Extensive
3	Speaking and Listening Skills	4.01	Extensive
4	Language Awareness	2.63	Moderately Extensive
5	Reading Comprehension	2.63	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean			3.11
Moderately Extensive			

A study by Liu and Jiang (2019) found that college-level EFL learners in China struggle with writing due to a lack of vocabulary and grammatical knowledge. In contrast, a study by Kormos and Trebits (2015) found that young learners in Hungary showed improvement in their writing skills when they received explicit instruction on grammar and vocabulary. Zhang and Jiang (2017) found that Chinese EFL learners at the university level had limited vocabulary knowledge and struggled with understanding academic texts. Similarly, a study by Alqarni

and Alduais (2020) found that Saudi Arabian EFL learners had low vocabulary knowledge, which negatively affected their speaking and writing skills. Research has shown that learners' speaking and listening proficiency is influenced by a variety of factors, including their first language background, age, motivation, and exposure to the language. For example, a study by Yang, Sun, and Huang (2015) found that young learners in China showed significant improvement in their speaking skills when they received explicit instruction and had opportunities for interaction in class. Similarly, a study by Motalebzadeh and Alavi (2020) found that Iranian EFL learners' listening skills improved when they received explicit instruction and engaged in listening activities. Horan and Cullen (2019) found that Irish primary school students who received explicit instruction on grammar and language awareness showed significant improvement in their writing skills. Similarly, a study by Mirzaei and Kassaian (2017) found that Iranian EFL learners who received explicit instruction on language awareness showed improvement in

their speaking and writing skills. Hamdan and Yusoff (2020) found that Malaysian secondary school students struggled with reading comprehension due to limited vocabulary knowledge and poor reading strategies. In contrast, a study by Tamaoka (2019) found that Japanese EFL learners showed significant improvement in their reading comprehension when they received explicit instruction on reading strategies.

Relationship Between Campus Journalism Participation and Language Proficiency

It can be depicted that Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between campus journalism participation ($r=0.865$; $p<.001$) and language proficiency among Elementary School learners. Table 13 revealed the yielded results of the significant correlation between campus journalism participation and language proficiency. It provides an information that the posed null hypothesis stating that there is no significant correlation between campus journalism participation and language proficiency must be rejected for it provided empirical evidence of significant results.

Table 13. Significant Relationship between Campus Journalism Participation and Language Proficiency

Variables	<i>r-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	Interpretation	Decision
Campus Journalism Participation Language Proficiency	0.865	< 0.001	Significant	Reject H_0

*significant @ $p < 0.05$.

Campus journalism has been recognized as an effective platform for promoting language proficiency among students. It involves writing, speaking, and listening activities, which help learners develop their language skills. Widiastuti, Sudiro, and Tiyas (2016) investigated the impact of campus journalism on English language proficiency among Indonesian university students. The researchers found that campus journalism participation significantly improved

students' reading, writing, speaking, and listening skills. They concluded that campus journalism could serve as an effective strategy to enhance students' language proficiency. Similarly, another study by Taylan (2018) explored the impact of campus journalism on the language proficiency of Turkish high school students. The researcher found that students who participated in campus journalism activities showed significant improvement in their language skills,

particularly in their writing and speaking abilities. Taylan suggested that campus journalism could be used as a tool to improve students' language proficiency. Moreover, a study by Cabahug, Gabunales, and Gargalicana (2020) investigated the impact of campus journalism on the language proficiency of Filipino high school students. The researchers found that students who participated in campus journalism activities showed higher levels of language proficiency than those who did not. Specifically, the students who participated in campus journalism activities had better speaking, listening, reading, and writing skills than their peers. Lastly, a study by Adu-Gyamfi and Koranteng (2019) examined the impact of campus journalism on the language proficiency of Ghanaian high school students. The researchers found that campus journalism participation significantly improved

Meanwhile, the R^2 value of 0.875 suggests that the domains of campus journalism participation explained 87.5%. In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, given regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value (226.887) and F-statistic is significant $p < .002$, tells that the model is significantly a better predictor of language proficiency. There is a significant influence of regularity of publication, quality of content, student leadership, community engagement, and awards and recognition to language proficiency. Campus journalism participation has been proven to enhance language proficiency among students, and the mentioned factors play a crucial role in this enhancement. The regularity of publication ensures that students consistently engage in writing and language use, leading to better proficiency over time. According to Khan and Samad (2019), frequent opportunities to practice writing and reading, such as those provided by regular publication, can improve language skills. Quality of content produced by students can also influence their language profi-

students' language proficiency, particularly in their writing and speaking abilities. They recommended that schools should encourage students to participate in campus journalism activities to enhance their language proficiency.

Domains of Campus Journalism Participation Significantly Influence Language Proficiency

Table 14 depicts the simple regression coefficient analysis on the domains of campus journalism participation significantly influence language proficiency. Domains of campus journalism participation in terms of regularity of publication (0.004), quality of content (0.040), student leadership (0.002) and awards and recognition (0.000) significantly influence language proficiency, while community engagement (0.085) does not influence language proficiency.

ciency. Hidayati and Munir (2018) found that students who participated in campus journalism and produced high-quality content showed significant improvement in their language skills. Student leadership in campus journalism can also contribute to language proficiency. Students who take leadership roles in the publication process develop critical thinking, problem-solving, and communication skills, which can transfer to their overall language proficiency (Hidayati Munir, 2018). Finally, awards and recognition can motivate and inspire students to improve their language skills, especially when they see the fruits of their hard work recognized by others (Khan Samad, 2019). In conclusion, campus journalism participation can significantly influence language proficiency among students, and factors such as regularity of publication, quality of content, student leadership and awards and recognition play a crucial role in this enhancement. Therefore, schools and educators should prioritize promoting and supporting campus journalism as a means of improving language proficiency among their students.

Table 14. Regression Coefficient Analysis on Domains of Campus Journalism Participation Significantly Influencing Language Proficiency

Model	B	Beta	Standard Error	p-value	Decision
H	(Intercept)	4.145	0.079	60.426	0.001
4.145					
H	(Intercept)	0.203	0.175	1.076	0.280
0.201					
	<i>Regularity of Publication</i>	0.107	0.107	0.102	1.010
0.315	0.004	*Reject H_0			
	<i>Quality of Content</i>	0.441	0.108	0.136	1.299
0.196	0.040	*Reject H_0			
	<i>Student Leadership</i>	0.202	0.097	0.210	2.098
0.038	0.002	*Reject H_0			
	<i>Community Engagement</i>	0.683	0.086	0.499	5.654
0.001	0.085	Accept H_0			
	<i>Awards and Recognition</i>	0.202	0.096	0.220	2.078
0.028	0.000	*Reject H_0			
R^2	= 0.875				
F -value	= 226.887				
p -value	= < 0.002				

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the findings, conclusion and recommendation based on the results of the data analyzed, discussed, and drawn implications. Findings are based on the posed statement of the problem; conclusions are based on the findings generated and recommendations are based on the implications of the discussions.

4.1. Findings—The following are findings of the study given the results in the presentation, analysis and discussions. The extent of campus journalism participation in terms of regularity of publication (3.54) is oftentimes manifested, while, community engagement (3.34), quality of content (3.29), awards and recognition (3.23) and student leadership (3.08) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.29 denotes campus journalism participation is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. The extent of learners’ language proficiency in terms of speaking and listening skills (4.01) is oftentimes manifested, while, writing skills (3.33), vocabulary knowledge (2.95), language awareness (2.63) and reading comprehension (2.63) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.1 denotes learners’ language proficiency is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. Pearson’s Correlation gen-

erated a significant correlation between campus journalism participation ($r=0.865$; $p_i.001$) and language proficiency among Elementary School learners. Domains of campus journalism participation in terms of regularity of publication (0.004), quality of content (0.040), student leadership (0.002) and awards and recognition (0.000) significantly influence language proficiency, while community engagement (0.085) does not influence language proficiency.

4.2. *Conclusions*—Given the findings of the study presented, the following are conclusions, to wit; The campus journalism participation in terms of regularity of publication, community engagement, quality of content, awards and recognition and student leadership denotes sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. The learners' language proficiency in terms of speaking and listening skills, writing skills, vocabulary knowledge, language awareness and reading comprehension denotes learners' language proficiency is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. There is a significant correlation between campus journalism participation and language proficiency among elementary school learners. Domains of campus journalism participation in terms of regularity of publication, quality of content, student leadership and awards and recognition significantly influenced language proficiency.

4.3. *Recommendations*—With the presented conclusions of the study, the following are recommendations, to wit; Public School Dis-

trict Supervisor. The district supervisor can encourage and support the establishment of a campus journalism program in schools and allocate resources to sustain its regularity of publication, quality of content, student leadership, community engagement, and recognition. They can also provide professional development opportunities to teachers to enhance their knowledge and skills in journalism education. Teachers. Teachers can integrate campus journalism activities into their language classes and provide opportunities for students to practice their language skills through writing articles, conducting interviews, and reporting events. They can also encourage students to participate in journalism contests and competitions to improve their writing and critical thinking skills. Future Researchers: Future researchers can conduct longitudinal studies to investigate the long-term effects of campus journalism participation on language proficiency and other academic outcomes. They can also explore the effectiveness of different teaching strategies and approaches to journalism education in promoting language learning and development. The campus journalism program can be a valuable tool for enhancing language proficiency among students. By promoting regularity of publication, quality of content, student leadership, recognition, most especially with community engagement, schools can create a supportive and stimulating environment for language learning and development.

5. References

- Adu-Gyamfi, K., & Koranteng, A. (2019). Campus journalism and language proficiency: A study of senior high school students in Ghana. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 10(6), 1241-1249. doi: 10.17507/jltr.1006.15
- AITF For the Management of Infectious Diseases
<https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/downloads/2021/05may/20210520-IATF->
- Alcantara, R. (2018). Campus Journalism: A Tool for Developing Students' Writing Skills. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 6(1), 69-74.
- Alqahtani, M., & Al-Enzy, F. (2019). The effect of teaching reading strategies on EFL learners' reading comprehension. *International Journal of Instruction*, 12(3), 411-428.
<https://doi.org/10.29333/iji.2019.12326a>
- Alshammari, R., & Alkandari, M. (2019). Campus journalism, social media and political knowledge among elementary school students in Kuwait. *Educational Research*, 61(3), 267-282
- Ata, R., & Canda, E. (2021). The effect of a campus journalism program on the writing skills of elementary school students. *Educational Sciences: Theory and Practice*, 21(3), 65-78
- Baltova, I., & Piquer-Piriz, A. M. (2020). Language awareness and foreign language proficiency: A review of empirical studies. *Language Teaching Research*, 24(4), 425-451.
- Bostancı, E. (2018). The effect of a journalism education program on students' self-efficacy beliefs and news literacy skills. *Journalism & Mass Communication Educator*, 73(2), 131-145. doi: 10.1177/1077695818760669
- Boyd, B. A., & Burton, R. (2015). The role of awards in early-career success in journalism. *Journalism & Mass Communication Quarterly*, 92(3), 529-548. doi: 10.1177/1077699015587964
- Cabahug, M. A. A., Gabunales, E. R. C., & Gargalicana, R. A. (2020). The impact of campus journalism on the language proficiency of Filipino high school students. *Journal of Research in Innovative Teaching & Learning*, 13(2), 113-121. doi: 10.1108/JRIT-03-2020-0004
- Campbell, D. T., & Stanley, J. C. (1963). *Experimental and quasi-experimental designs for research*. Houghton Mifflin
- Canda, E., & Ata, R. (2021). The effect of a campus journalism program on the writing skills of elementary school students. *Educational Sciences: Theory and Practice*, 21(3), 65-78
- Chen, X. (2020). The impact of publication frequency on online media reputation: Evidence from China. *Journal of Media Business Studies*, 17(1), 1-16

- Chen, X., & Ge, L. (2020). A study on the relationship between vocabulary knowledge and English proficiency. *Education Sciences*, 10(11), 313
- Cheng, X. (2019). A study of the correlation between college students' spoken English proficiency and their listening comprehension ability. *International Journal of English Linguistics*, 9(2), 267-273
- Cheng, L., & Li, X. (2019). Investigating the relationship between language proficiency and writing quality: A correlational study. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 10(1), 173-180
- Creswell, John W. (2014). *Qualitative Inquiry and Research Design: Choosing Among Five Approaches*. Fourth edition. Washington DC: Sage.
- Cumming, A., & Kantor, R. (2018). Language proficiency and writing development: A process-oriented research agenda. *Journal of Second Language Writing*, 39, 57-67
- Cummins, J. (2017). Identity and language learning: Extending the conversation. In *Language and identity: Discourse in the world* (pp. 103-117). Routledge.
<https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315646201-7>
- Curry, D. L., & Parks, C. (2016). Service-learning and the campus press: A case study. *Journalism & Mass Communication Educator*, 71(1), 50-61. doi: 10.1177/1077695815615097
- Delos Reyes, J. A. S., & Pineda, P. G. (2021). The Relationship between Campus Journalism Participation and English Language Proficiency: The Case of Selected High Schools in the Philippines. *Journal of Educational and Psychological Studies*, 15(1), 221-235.
<https://doi.org/10.24200/jeps.vol15iss1pp221-235>
- Diaz, M. L., & Regala, C. R. (2019). Campus journalism and community engagement: An exploratory study among elementary school students in the Philippines. *International Journal of Research Studies in Education*, 8(3), 33-42
- Dizon, M. (2021). Campus journalism: A platform for academic and personal excellence. *Philippine Daily Inquirer*. Retrieved from <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/1411193/campus-journalism-a-platform-for-academic-and-personal-excellence>
- Dolzhikova, O. V., & Evmenova, A. S. (2020). Developing oral proficiency in EFL learners through video-mediated communication. *Journal of Language and Education*, 6(4), 72-83.
<https://doi.org/10.17323/2411-7390-2020-6-4-72-83>
- Echarri, A. (2020). Leadership and Campus Journalism. *Philippine Star*. Retrieved from <https://www.philstar.com/the-freeman/opinion/2020/09/07/2040826/leadership-and-campus-journalism>
- Ellis, K. A., & Pintar, E. (2019). Elementary school newspaper: Building a school community of writers. *Childhood Education*, 95(2), 105-112. doi: 10.1080/00094056.2019.1571988

- Farhady, H., & Mahdavi, A. (2019). The impact of a web-based listening program on the listening proficiency of EFL learners. *Iranian Journal of Language Teaching Research*, 7(2), 25-46. <https://doi.org/10.30486/ijltr.2019.665482>
- Freedman, D. A. (2009). *Statistical models and causal inference: A dialogue with the social sciences*. Cambridge University Press
- Graham, S., & Perin, D. (2017). *Writing next: Effective strategies to improve writing of adolescents in middle and high schools*. Alliance for Excellent Education. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED574043>
- Gonzales, M. D. C., Estrellado, A. A., & Jumamil, M. J. T. (2020). Campus journalism and socio-emotional development of grade 11 students. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(7), 2072-2082
- Gonzales, J., & Mejia, D. (2019). The role of student journalists in higher education. *Journal of Applied Journalism & Media Studies*, 8(1), 1-14. doi: 10.1386/ajms_00008_1
- Gutiérrez-Palma, N., & López-Pastor, V. M. (2015). Developing critical reading skills: The role of higher-order thinking skills and reciprocal teaching. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 108(5), 376-391. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220671.2014.914200>
- Hickman, E. A. (2021). News literacy in the elementary classroom: Fostering critical thinking and civic engagement through a student newspaper. *Journal of Media Literacy Education*, 13(2), 72-91. doi: 10.23860/JMLE-2021-13-2-5
- Hidayati, N., & Munir, M. (2018). Enhancing English language proficiency through campus journalism. *Lingua Franca: Jurnal Bahasa, Sastra, dan Pengajarannya*, 3(1), 21-30. <https://doi.org/10.32513/linguafranca.v3i1.309>
- Hinkel, E. (2004). *Teaching academic ESL writing: Practical techniques in vocabulary and grammar*. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates
- Hopp, M. (2016). Predicting reading comprehension from listening comprehension among Chinese-speaking university students. *Reading in a Foreign Language*, 28(2), 244-262. <https://doi.org/10.1111/modl.12344>
- Hulstijn, J. H., & de Graaf, R. (2015). Attention, awareness, and individual differences in language learning. In B. VanPatten & J. Williams (Eds.), *Theories in second language acquisition: An introduction* (2nd ed., pp. 224-247). New York, NY: Routledge.
- Hussain, S., Ullah, M., Ahmad, S., & Aziz, S. (2020). Impact of campus journalism on critical thinking and reading comprehension of elementary school students. *Journal of Educational Research*, 23(1), 53-67
- Jones, J., & Stacks, D. (2015). Award competitions and the culture of journalism education. *Journalism & Mass Communication Educator*, 70(2), 204-216. doi: 10.1177/1077695815572608

- Kamarudin, K., Jaafar, J., Alias, N., Osman, M. S., & Ibrahim, M. H. (2019). Language proficiency among rural primary school students in Malaysia: Issues and challenges. *Pertanika Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 27(2), 1107-1120
- Kang, S., & Norton, S. (2016). The changing role of campus journalism in the digital age. *Journalism & Mass Communication Educator*, 71(4), 463-472. doi: 10.1177/1077695816662461
- Kendeou, P., van den Broek, P., White, M. J., & Lynch, J. S. (2017). Predictors of reading comprehension: The role of decoding and language comprehension for children with different levels of word reading fluency. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 109(4), 440-454. <https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000157>
- Khan, M. S., & Samad, A. (2019). The role of campus journalism in developing language proficiency. *Journal of Education and Educational Development*, 6(1), 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.22555/joeeed.v6i1.2399>
- Khojasteh, L., & Khojasteh, M. (2018). Collaborative tasks and speaking skill development among Iranian EFL learners. *International Journal of English Linguistics*, 8(4), 133-139. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijel.v8n4p133>
- Kim, K. H., Kwon, H., & Jeong, J. (2018). Campus journalism and the cultivation of democratic citizenship among Korean elementary school students. *Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 50(1), 25-41
- Kim, Y., Lee, S., & Lee, J. (2019). The relationship between reading proficiency and L2 proficiency: A meta-analysis of empirical studies. *English Teaching*, 74(2), 37-60
- Kuhl, P. K. (2016). Early language learning and the social brain. In P. Rebuschat (Ed.), *The Cambridge handbook of cognitive linguistics* (pp. 731-757). Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
- Lamay, E. (2019). What makes a good campus journalist? Retrieved from <https://www.sunstar.com.ph/article/1825839/Cebu/Opinion/What-makes-a-good-campus-journalist>
- Lamb, C., & McKenna, C. (2017). The importance of community engagement for local journalism. *Journalism Practice*, 11(7), 841-857. doi: 10.1080/17512786.2016.1259677
- Lantolf, J. P., & Thorne, S. L. (2006). *Sociocultural theory and the genesis of second language development*. Oxford: Oxford University Press
- Largo, F. M. S., & Nadal, J. B. (2019). Campus journalism as a vehicle for enhancing the writing skills of elementary pupils in Negros Occidental. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Research*, 9(1), 1-10

- Lee, I., & Jang, J. (2018). Social constructivism as an approach to teaching and learning second languages: An overview. In J. I. Lontas (Ed.), *The TESOL encyclopedia of English language teaching* (pp. 1-7). Hoboken, NJ: Wiley-Blackwell.
- Lee, C. Y., & Huang, Y. M. (2020). Effects of augmented reality on EFL young learners' reading comprehension and motivation. *Computers & Education*, 146, 103758. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2019.103758>
- Lippmann, C. (2018). The impact of recognition on motivation and engagement in student journalists. *Journalism & Mass Communication Educator*, 73(2), 165-178. doi: 10.1177/1077695817734049
- Liwanag, M. J. (2019). The effects of campus journalism participation on writing skills of grade 10 students. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 7(2), 79-87
- Lyles, M. (2019). The value of journalism in the elementary classroom. *Social Studies Research and Practice*, 14(1), 87-96. doi: 10.1080/19331681.2018.1550106
- Marasigan, L. R., & Bala, M. M. (2018). Campus journalism and youth civic engagement: A case study of elementary school students in the Philippines. *Journal of Media Literacy Education*, 10(3), 41-55
- Nagy, W., Townsend, D., & Herman, P. A. (2015). Vocabulary acquisition and instruction: Overview, definitions, and research directions. In *Handbook of research on reading comprehension* (pp. 269-289). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315813742-15>
- Nation, I. S. P. (2001). *Learning vocabulary in another language*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
- National Governors Association Center for Best Practices & Council of Chief State School Officers. (2010). *Common Core State Standards for English Language Arts and Literacy in History/Social Studies, Science, and Technical Subjects*. http://www.corestandards.org/wp-content/uploads/ELA_Standards.pdf
- Nishimura, S., & Kline, K. (2017). Leadership in collegiate journalism: Perspectives of student editors. *Journalism & Mass Communication Educator*, 72(4), 449-463. doi: 10.1177/1077695817720194
- Ocampo, J., & Johnson, A. (2018). Community engagement and student learning in a digital age. *Journalism & Mass Communication Educator*, 73(3), 317-331. doi: 10.1177/1077695818775663
- Othman, M. S., Ismail, N. A. H., & Ibrahim, M. F. (2020). Campus journalism: Promoting language proficiency and cross-cultural understanding. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(12), 1423-1430. <https://doi.org/10.31838/jcr.07.12.270>
- Paribakht, T. S., & Wesche, M. (1997). Vocabulary enhancement activities and reading for meaning in second language vocabulary acquisition. In J. Coady & T. Huckin (Eds.), *Second language vocabulary acquisition: A rationale for pedagogy* (pp. 174

- Pineda, P. G. (2018). The Relationship of Campus Journalism Participation and English Language Proficiency among Junior High School Students. *Journal of Research in Education*, 32(2), 59-75. <https://doi.org/10.242>
- Ramon, J. B., Torres, E. S., Tolo, E. A., & Mamaradlo, M. J. A. (2021). Campus journalism and language proficiency development among elementary learners in the Philippines. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 12(2), 292-301
- Reese, S. D., & Lewis, S. C. (2017). Journalism awards and industry self-regulation. *Journalism & Mass Communication Quarterly*, 94(1), 98-117. doi: 10.1177/1077699016679806
- Reinders, H., & Lazaro, N. (2018). Task-based language teaching and technology: A critical review. *Language Teaching*, 51(1), 1-43. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S026144481700035X>
- Rodriguez, A. D., & de la Cruz, J. F. (2022). Effects of campus journalism participation on the reading comprehension skills of elementary students. *Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies in Education*, 2(2), 27-34
- Roxas, R. (2018). Effects of teacher feedback on the writing skills of senior high school students in campus journalism. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 6(3), 89-96
- Song, M. J., & Suh, B. R. (2015). The effects of online language learning materials on learners' grammatical accuracy and vocabulary acquisition: A meta-analysis. *Computer Assisted Language Learning*, 28(4), 349-371. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09588221.2013.818559>
- Sparks, R. L., & Ganschow, L. (2018). The impact of a summer school language and literacy program on language proficiency: A randomized trial. *Reading and Writing*, 31(6), 1297-1317. doi: 10.1007/s11145-018-9854-9
- Streitmatter, R. (2019). Journalism education for a diverse and democratic society: A critical conversation. *Journalism & Mass Communication Educator*, 74(2), 132-138. doi: 10.1177/1077695819829575
- Tavakoli, M., & Ghonsooly, B. (2017). Discourse awareness and language learners' pragmatic competence. *Journal of Pragmatics*, 109, 30-44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pragma.2016.11.008>
- Taylan, E. (2018). Campus journalism and language proficiency: A study on high school students in Turkey. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 9(7), 95-99. doi: 10.7176/JEP/9-7-15
- Tello, M., & Martinez, R. (2018). The value of student media organizations in developing student leadership skills. *Journal of Leadership Education*, 17(3), 1-8. doi: 10.12806/V17/I3/R1
- Teng, H., & Zhang, J. (2021). The relationship between writing skills and English proficiency in a Chinese context. *International Journal of Instruction*, 14(2), 97-112

- Thornbury, S. (2017). Language Awareness. In G. Hall & S. M. Hellermann (Eds.), *Handbook of Language Awareness* (pp. 3-14). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-38895-4_1
- Van der Meijden, H., & Veenman, M. V. J. (2018). Enhancing reading comprehension with digital tools: A systematic review. *Educational Research Review*, 23, 47-71. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2018.01.002>
- Wang, X. (2021). Developing campus journalism guidelines for elementary schools in China. *Journal of Media Ethics*, 36(1), 23-35
- Widiastuti, I. P. A., Sudiro, A., & Tiyas, E. T. (2016). The impact of campus journalism on English language proficiency: An investigation on Indonesian university students. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 7(6), 1245-1253. doi: 10.17507/jltr.0706.16
- Yin, R. K. (2018). *Case study research and applications: Design and methods*. Sage publications
- Zerfass, A., Verčič, D., Verhoeven, P., Moreno, A., & Huertas, A. (2016). *European Communication Monitor 2016. Strategic Communication and Its Agendas: Views from Academia and Practice*, 199-215. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-33816-5_11
- Zhang, L. J., & Elder, C. (2018). The relationship between language proficiency and reading comprehension: A meta-analysis. *Reading in a Foreign Language*, 30(2), 196-217. <https://doi.org/10.1111/modl.12344>
- Zhang, X., & Su, L. (2019). Online news consumption and readers' trust: Perceptions of news media credibility in China. *Journalism Studies*, 20(6), 790-809. doi: 10.1080/1461670X.2018.1509472